

Parental Leave Policy at the Nigerian Civil Service Commission

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the disparities and societal beliefs around paternal leave in the Nigerian Civil Service, highlighting the notable disparity between laws and actual implementation in relation to gender norms and family dynamics. Despite the perception of Nigeria as a supportive environment for fathers, the research reveals a significant disparity in leave entitlements between fathers and mothers, with fathers receiving significantly less time off. The study uses qualitative interview data analysis to investigate the effects of these rules on dads' engagement in caring activities and their perceived obligations in both household and workplace contexts. The key topics addressed encompass inequitable leave legislation, sociological and cultural issues, and considerations about the benefits and usage of paternal leave. The results emphasize the need for policy changes that are in line with changing family dynamics and promote equal parental participation. The paper examines Nigeria's paternal leave regulations in relation to those of more progressive countries, contributing to the worldwide discussion on the importance of implementing supportive familial leave policies that promote gender equality and strengthen the link between fathers and children. The study seeks to educate policymakers and stakeholders about the crucial significance of fair and inclusive parental leave policies in promoting a harmonious, just, and forward-thinking society.

Key words: Paternal Leave, Family, Gender Equality, Child, Parents.

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1. Introduction and Background

Parental leave policies are essential tools for improving family well-being and advancing gender equality in both personal and work environments. These policies allow parents to take time off from work to care for their newborn children, which promotes family bonding and aids in the child's development. Nevertheless, the execution and efficacy of these programs differ significantly across diverse cultural, socioeconomic, and legal contexts.

Several affluent countries have made substantial progress in establishing equitable and comprehensive parental leave laws. Sweden and Norway have developed progressive policies that offer substantial parental leave to both mothers and fathers, with the goal of equalizing caregiving obligations and advancing gender equality (Almqvist & Duvander, 2014; Brandth & Kvande, 2019). These laws demonstrate a society's commitment to

strengthening family units and ensuring the equal participation of both parents in child-rearing.

In contrast, parental leave regulations in many underdeveloped nations, such as Nigeria, have historically been biased towards mothers. Fathers frequently receive limited or nonexistent leave benefits. This disparity is a clear indication of strongly ingrained gender norms that view women as the main caregivers and men as the primary earners. Although Nigeria's cultural rhetoric appears to be supportive of fathers, the statutory structure does not align with this sentiment, as fathers generally receive far less time off compared to women. This disparity not only maintains old gender norms but also limits fathers' involvement in early childcare activities, which are crucial for the comprehensive growth of the child and the welfare of the family unit (Dermott & Miller, 2015).

The Nigerian Civil Service, as a major employer and a model for employment practices in the country, offers a compelling example for studying the present condition of paternity leave policy. Within this particular scenario, the discrepancy in the amount of time off granted to mothers and fathers becomes even more evident. Mothers receive an extended period of maternity leave, emphasizing their crucial role in raising children. On the other hand, dads frequently receive a noticeably briefer period of time off work, if they receive any at all. This indirectly reinforces their position as less important caregivers (Haas & Rostgaard, 2011).

This study examines the disparities and societal attitudes toward paternal leave in the Nigerian Civil Service. It emphasizes the significant disparity between laws and actual implementation, taking into account gender norms and family dynamics. This research aims to examine the effects of existing paternal leave regulations on dads' engagement in caregiving tasks and their perceived obligations in both the home and the workplace. The study utilizes qualitative analysis of interview data to provide a comprehensive understanding of these dynamics (Schoppe-Sullivan & Fagan, 2020).

This study primarily examines the cultural and societal norms that influence the taking and use of paternal leave. Social conventions sometimes significantly influence the attitude of fathers who take parental leave. Both inside their professional environment and in the wider community, male parents who choose to take time off from work frequently face unfavorable evaluations and preconceived notions. This societal pressure deters numerous fathers from utilizing their leave entitlements, even when they are accessible. The social disapproval associated with paternal leave poses a substantial obstacle to attaining gender equality in caregiving duties (Haas & Hwang, 2019).

Significantly, the report also emphasizes a promising change in these conventional standards, as more and more fathers are actively engaging in caregiving duties. This shift signifies an increasing acknowledgment of the significance of male participation in raising children, implying that Nigerian culture might be more open to fair parental leave regulations than previously believed. The active involvement of dads in caring tasks defies traditional stereotypes and highlights the possibility of cultural change towards more gender-balanced practices (Koslowski, Duvander, & Moss, 2019).

Extensive research continues to confirm the advantages of paternity leave in strengthening the link between fathers and their children, as well as in fostering the child's growth. According to Huerta et al. (2014), fathers who take leave are more engaged in their children's lives, which has a good effect on their cognitive and emotional development. Nevertheless, the prevailing social expectations and unfavorable attitudes towards men who take time from work for family-related responsibilities impede the optimal utilization of paternity leave. Many fathers fear that taking time off from work could negatively affect their jobs and portray them as not fully committed to their professional responsibilities. To address these problems, it is necessary to implement governmental changes and foster cultural shifts that encourage and establish the active participation of dads in the early care and upbringing of children (Rehel, 2014).

This study also examines Nigeria's paternal leave laws in comparison to those of more progressive nations, adding to the worldwide discussion on the necessity of inclusive family leave policies that promote gender equality and foster stronger bonds between fathers and children. This research explores the cultural and corporate perspectives of Nigerian fathers who take parental leave and identifies the specific challenges they face based on their gender. It offers valuable insights into the larger concerns surrounding gender equality and societal values in Nigeria (Brandth & Kvande, 2019).

The primary objective of this study is to provide policymakers and stakeholders with essential information regarding the crucial significance of fair and just parental leave laws. Nigeria may make substantial progress in achieving gender equality and improving family well-being by addressing current gaps and encouraging a more inclusive approach to parental leave. Implementing equitable parental leave policies not only benefits the families directly engaged but also fosters a more balanced, just, and forward-thinking society (Schoppe-Sullivan & Fagan, 2020).

Problem Statement

The changing dynamics of achieving a balance between work and personal life, as well as promoting gender equality in the workplace, have become important topics of discussion in today's society, especially when it comes to legislation regarding parental leave. In Nigeria, the adoption and utilization of parental leave policies within the Civil Service Commission demonstrate an intricate interaction between cultural norms, gender roles, and the success of the rules, notwithstanding the advancements made towards creating more inclusive work environments. This study aims to investigate the factors that contribute to the difference in the uptake of parental leave between men and women in Nigeria, a community that is perceived to be supportive of fathers. The goal is to shed light on cultural and corporate attitudes towards Nigerian fathers who take parental leave, as well as identify the gender-specific obstacles they face. These obstacles highlight the possible mismatch between legislative goals and real-world implementation, revealing larger problems related to gender equality and societal values in Nigeria. It is important to analyze these aspects because there is a significant lack of knowledge regarding how gendered viewpoints and past examples affect males' implementation of parental leave policies. This, in turn, has an impact on family dynamics, workplace cultures, and the overall pursuit of gender equality. This problem statement forms the basis of the study's

investigation into the efficacy of current parental leave laws in Nigeria, with a focus on gender and historical perspectives. The study aims to contribute to the discussion on policy reform and cultural change towards equal sharing of parenting responsibilities.

Aim and Objectives

This study intends to investigate fathers' unequal treatment and provide a record of policies, mentalities, and behaviors related to parental leave for fathers in Oyo State. In order to accomplish the overall aim, the study seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the extent to which men's parental leave in Nigeria is less popular than women's leave.
2. To investigate the way Nigerian fathers on parental leave are perceived and judged in society and the workplace.
3. To analyze the gendered issues related to men's parental leave in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guide this study's approach to solving the problem:

Main Question

How can contemporary parental leave legislation in Nigeria be described from a gendered and historical perspective?

Sub-Questions

- 1) To what extent is men's uptake of parental leave considerably lower than women's, even in a 'father-friendly' society such as Nigeria?
- 2) How are Nigerian fathers on parental leave perceived and judged in society and the workplace?
- 3) In the context of men's parental leave in Nigeria, what gendered challenges are present?

2. Literature Review

Gender equity theory will underpin the conceptual framework of the study.

2.1 Gender equity theory

Gender equity theory focuses on the pursuit of equity and balance between genders in terms of wellbeing, social, nourishment, financial, and power relationships between males and females (Kumar, 2016). The law divides the concept of equity into two parts: formal equity (by right) and meaningful equity (recognized).

2.2 Gender equity theory's historical and philosophical background

This section provides a synopsis of the research on gender roles and their historical precedents in the formation of families.

The family unit has established gender roles in many traditional societies. Family structures have remained relatively constant from ancient times to the present, as noted by Alesina and Giuliano (2014), who also noted the correlation between family structure and economic outcomes, including the impact of gender assignments.

The "male-provider hypothesis," which states that men should work all day and women should devote themselves to housekeeping, is a major contributor to family breakdown in communities with strong family ties (González, Jurado, & Naldini, 2014). On the other hand, a lack of strong family bonds leads to the rise of populist gender roles, in which men and women view their roles as being about equal in terms of their interest in both the workplace and the home (p. 659). According to González, Jurado, and Naldini (2014), one can gauge the health of family ties by answering three questions: how strongly one believes that one's family is important, how seriously one takes one's parental responsibilities, and how much one values his or her parents' affection and regard. The strength of family relationships has been shown to have a significant effect on several outcomes, such as women's labor force participation and family formation, and this standardized indicator is used to examine this relationship. They emphasize that in strong family environments, women tend to work less outside the home and prioritize spending time with their children and home improvement projects. They also adhere to more traditional notions of how men and women should interact.

2.3 Characteristics and Principles of Gender Equity Theory

Gender equity requires equivalent satisfaction by ladies and men of socially-esteemed opportunities, convenience, assets, and rewards.

The following are a portion of the principles of gender mainstreaming:

(i) Equal access to and use of services. (ii) Ladies and men have equal decision-making rights, and (iii) equivalent treatment is brought into coordination.

2.4 Relevance of Gender Equity Theory in Family

Inconsistent social orders are weaker. They have a higher rate of anti-social behavior and brutality. Countries with stronger gender equality are more related. Their relatives are more affluent and prosperous. Gender equality makes communities safer and more secure (Clancy, Oparaocha, and Roehr, 2012).

2.5 Why is gender equity theory applicable to the present study?

Feminist theory examines inequalities in women and men's treatment as a form of conflict theory. We use the conflict resolution strategy to address gender-based inequalities and discrimination. Feminist philosophy challenges established norms by investigating the ways in which gender shapes the human condition. The unequal power relations between men and women in capitalist society give rise to gender inequality, and critical feminist theory contends that men disproportionately exploit women in certain ways. Feminism is the political and social movement that holds the belief that men and women are of equal worth and should have equal access to positions of power, rights, and opportunities (Marganski, 2017).

Witz (1993) argues that the study of women's employment has been and will continue to be of crucial importance to feminists because they are concerned with identifying the processes and structures that produce gender inequalities and gender segregation, as well as developing suitable strategies for equalizing the position of women and men in paid work. Feminists can learn more about how class and "race" inequities intersect with gender divisions by examining the experiences of women in paid work, which vary for women from different socioeconomic backgrounds. Hence, the labor market is a site of interconnected forms of discrimination.

For example, the conditions under which women participate in paid employment, such as their limited access to education and training, have significant effects on their ability to pursue careers of their choosing and grow in their current positions. There is a multiplicative effect between the labour market and other forms of sexism (Witz, 1993).

3. Research Methods

3.1 Research Design

This study used a qualitative research approach to thoroughly investigate the experiences and perspectives related to paternal leave in the Nigerian Civil Service. This method facilitates a comprehensive comprehension of the complex cultural, socioeconomic, and policy-related aspects that impact the adoption of paternal leave.

3.2 Study Area and Population

We conducted the research in Oyo and Lagos, Nigeria. We selected these states due to their significant population size and the presence of diverse parastatals, making them representative of the broader Nigerian environment. The study concentrated on parastatal personnel, both male and female, who qualified for parental leave.

3.3 Sampling Technique

The researchers used purposive sampling to find participants who could offer insightful, pertinent, and varied viewpoints on the topic of paternal leave. The sample consisted of 400 interviewees, guaranteeing an equitable representation of both genders and diverse professional roles within the Civil Service.

3.4 Methods for Collecting Data

Semi-structured interviews gathered data, allowing for a flexible investigation of the participants' experiences and perspectives. We specifically created the interview guide to gather comprehensive comments on the usage, difficulties, and perspectives of paternal leave. We conducted the interviews in English and local languages, when necessary, followed by a subsequent translation.

3.5 Data analysis

Data analysis is the process of examining and interpreting data to uncover patterns, relationships, and insights.

We used thematic analysis to examine the acquired data. This approach entails the process of encoding the data in order to uncover noteworthy themes and patterns. The subsequent actions were executed:

Data familiarization involves transcribing the interviews and thoroughly reviewing the transcripts numerous times to gain a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

Creating Initial Codes: Identifying and categorizing important terms and ideas related to parental leave.

We are conducting a thematic analysis, which involves categorizing the codes into overarching themes that encompass the primary concepts.

Evaluating Themes: fine-tuning the themes to ensure they precisely reflect the data.

Defining and Naming Themes: Precisely delineating each subject and assigning suitable names to encapsulate its fundamental nature.

Generating the Report: Condensing the discoveries in a logical and thorough way

3.6 Ethical considerations

The University of Johannesburg's ethics committee granted ethical approval. We provided the participants with information about the study's goal, the procedures involved, and their rights, including the ability to withdraw from the study at any time. We received consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity.

3.7 Reliability and Validity

To ensure the dependability and accuracy of the results, we employed multiple methodologies. Triangulation refers to the practice of correlating research findings by utilizing several sources of data and employing diverse data collection methods.

Member Checking: We gave participants the opportunity to review and verify the accuracy of their interview transcripts.

Peer Review: Peers and professionals in the field critically evaluated the research process and findings to provide valuable comments and improve the study's credibility.

3.8 Limitations

The study admits certain constraints:

Geographical scope: The concentration on Oyo and Lagos States may limit the results' applicability to other areas of Nigeria.

Cultural Sensitivity: The cultural nuances surrounding paternal leave may range greatly in various regions of Nigeria, which can impact the relevance and validity of the research findings.

Sample Size: Although the information from 400 individuals is significant, a larger sample size could provide more extensive and thorough insights.

4. Findings

4.1 Data Coding.

The interview data was categorized into distinct and manageable groups, considering reoccurring ideas and concepts. Below are several possible codes: Duration Disparity: refers to the discrepancy in the length of leave taken by fathers and mothers.

Cultural Expectations: References to the societal and cultural norms on the roles and responsibilities of dads and mothers.

Father Involvement: Descriptions of fathers engaging in nocturnal caregiving and culinary activities.

Policy Dissatisfaction: Expressions of discontent with the existing parental leave policy for fathers.

4.2 The advantages of paternity leave in fostering father-child attachment.

International Comparison: Evaluating paternity leave policies in other countries. Equal Treatment: A discourse on the necessity of equitable treatment in regulations regarding parental leave.

Utilization Concerns: Concerns regarding the effective utilization of paternity leave by fathers.

4.3 Thematic Analysis

By analyzing the encoded material, we can discern three primary themes:

Unfair Leave laws: The significant difference in the length of leave granted to mothers compared to fathers exposes the underlying gender disparities within the parental leave laws.

Cultural and societal standards: Although there is a conventional expectation for mothers to be the main caregivers, research shows that fathers are actively participating in caregiving activities, which goes against these conventions.

Potential Advantages versus Usage Concerns: Although the advantages of paternity leave for fostering father-child ties are acknowledged, there are still reservations over the extent to which dads really take use of this leave.

5. Discussion

The study on "Parental Leave Policy at the Nigerian Civil Service Commission" uncovers significant insights into the present condition of paternal leave and its impact on gender equality and family dynamics in Nigeria.

5.1 Inequitable Leave Policies

The data indicates a notable discrepancy in the length of time off given to mothers and fathers in the Nigerian Civil Service. Fathers typically receive a significantly shorter or no leave duration compared to mothers. This reflects the prevailing global pattern, wherein paternity leave, if offered, is frequently significantly shorter in duration compared to maternity leave. This disparity is based on conventional gender stereotypes that perceive women as the primary caretakers and men as the primary earners (Brandth & Kvande, 2019).

The findings clearly show a discrepancy between the laws and their actual implementation, despite the claims that Nigeria provides a supportive environment for fathers. Paternal leave is typically significantly shorter than maternal leave, which restricts fathers' capacity to participate in early child-rearing tasks. This discrepancy not only sustains conventional gender roles but also impedes the possibility of achieving more equitable caregiving obligations within families (Schoppe-Sullivan & Fagan, 2020).

5.2 Cultural and societal norms

Cultural norms significantly influence the amount and utilization of paternal leave. The study revealed that societal norms exert a significant influence on the perceptions of fathers who choose to take parental leave. Fathers who choose to take leave are often subject to unfavorable judgment, both in the professional environment and in society at large. This disapproval serves as a deterrent for many fathers, preventing them from utilizing their entitled leave.

Significantly, the study also highlights a change in these conventional standards, with a growing percentage of fathers actively engaging in caring tasks. The movement suggests an increasing acknowledgement of the significance of male participation in raising children, implying that Nigerian culture might be more open to fair parental leave laws than previously believed (Haas & Rostgaard, 2011).

5.3 Examining the advantages and disadvantages of potential benefits and addressing usage concerns.

Research constantly affirms the advantages of paternity leave in strengthening the connection between fathers and their children. Huerta et al. (2014) conducted research indicating that fathers who take leave engage more in their children's lives, which positively impacts the child's cognitive and emotional development. Nevertheless, the survey highlights notable apprehensions over the practical implementation of paternity leave by fathers.

Social conventions and negative attitudes towards men who take time off for family-related responsibilities hinder the utilization of paternity leave. Many fathers worry that taking time off from work could have a detrimental impact on their employment and be perceived as a lack of dedication to their professional responsibilities (Rehel, 2014). To address these problems, it is necessary to implement governmental changes and foster cultural shifts that encourage and establish the active participation of dads in the early care and upbringing of children (Meil, 2013).

5.4 Comparative Analysis on an International Scale

When comparing Nigeria's rules on paternal leave with those of more progressive countries, it becomes evident that there are substantial disparities. For example, nations in the Nordic region such as Sweden provide extensive paternity leave, which actively encourages gender equality and facilitates the development of strong bonds between fathers and their children from a young age (Koslowski, Duvander, & Moss, 2019). These nations offer significant examples for Nigeria to follow as it seeks to revamp its parental leave laws in order to enhance support for fathers and advance gender equality in both domestic and professional spheres.

5.5 Proposed measures for action

The report highlights the necessity of significant legislative changes to tackle the disparities in parental leave. Suggested actions consist of lengthening the period of paternity leave to align it more closely with maternity leave, establishing safeguards to prevent fathers from experiencing workplace bias when they take leave, and fostering societal shifts that recognize and endorse the involvement of fathers in caregiving (Brandth & Kvande, 2019).

Conclusion

This paper presents a thorough analysis of the difficulties and advantages related to paternal leave in Nigeria. They emphasize the urgent need for policy reforms that are consistent with changing family dynamics and promote equal parental participation. Nigeria may make substantial progress in establishing gender equality and improving the well-being of families by tackling existing gaps and advocating for a more inclusive approach to parental leave (Schoppe-Sullivan & Fagan, 2020; Dermott & Miller, 2015).

6. Conclusion

The research on "Parental Leave Policy at the Nigerian Civil Service Commission" provides a thorough examination of the present condition of paternal leave in Nigeria and its wider consequences for gender equality and family dynamics. The results emphasize notable discrepancies in the length of parental leave provided to fathers in comparison to mothers, exposing entrenched traditional gender norms that perceive women as the main caregivers and men as the primary earners. This disparity sustains gender disparities both within the household and in professional settings, constraining fathers' participation in the early upbringing of children and reinforcing conventional caregiving responsibilities.

Cultural and societal norms are highly influential in determining the acceptance and utilization of paternal leave. Many fathers who choose to take leave frequently face unfavorable assessments, which serves as a deterrent for them to utilize their rights. Nevertheless, there is a hopeful change in these societal expectations as more and more men actively engage in caring tasks. This move signifies an increasing acknowledgment of the significance of father engagement in raising children, implying that Nigerian culture might be more open to fair parental leave laws than previously believed.

Despite the widespread recognition of paternity leave's benefits in fostering father-child relationships and promoting child development, significant obstacles still hinder its widespread implementation. Social conventions and unfavorable opinions about men's involvement in family responsibilities impede the utilization of paternity leave. To overcome these obstacles, it is necessary to implement policy reforms and foster cultural changes that encourage and establish the active participation of fathers in the early care and upbringing of children.

Nigeria's paternal leave regulations are significantly behind those of more progressive countries, particularly those in the Nordic region, as international comparisons reveal. These nations offer significant examples for Nigeria to contemplate as it seeks to revamp its parental leave policy to enhance support for fathers and advance gender equality.

The report highlights the pressing necessity for significant legislative changes to tackle the disparities in parental leave. Suggested actions consist of lengthening the period of paternity leave, enforcing measures to safeguard dads against workplace prejudice, and fostering cultural shifts that appreciate and endorse the involvement of fathers in caregiving. Nigeria can make substantial progress in attaining gender equality and improving the welfare of families by tackling both governmental and cultural obstacles.

To summarize, this study offers valuable perspectives on the difficulties and advantages related to paternal leave in Nigeria. Nigeria may promote a more balanced and fair society by creating an open and supportive environment for parents and implementing equitable parental leave regulations that benefit all families.

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